

Effects of virtual (digital) communication tools on patients and family member(s) in ICU: a mixed-method systematic review

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Effects of virtual (digital) communication tools on patients and family member(s) in ICU: a mixed-method systematic review

Review objectives

Does family-involved virtual communication have (positive) effect on the state of patients in intensive care units and their family member?

Keywords

family involvement, ICU, loneliness, telemedicine

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Searches

MEDLINE (PubMed), CINAHL, Cochrane Library, PsycINFO, PSYINDEX PROSPERO
Searching date was restricted from 2010 to the Sept 2023

Study design

RCT, Case studies, qualitative studies, reviews

-exclusion: reports

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Condition or domain being studied

The technical and structural environment of an intensive care unit represents a challenging, exceptional situation for both patients and relatives. In addition to physical suffering, patients often experience psychological distress such as fear, loss of control and loneliness. Many relatives also suffer from feelings of depression and sleep disorders. The “post-intensive care syndrome family” refers to a post-traumatic stress disorder that can last for months or years in relatives and adversely affect their quality of life and living situation. Intensive care treatment makes communication between patients and relatives almost impossible and can therefore increase the psychological stress. Hospitalized patients feel lonely and relatives have a high need for regular contact/information about the patients. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the communication barrier was significantly exacerbated by the restrictions and hygiene measures, so that numerous attempts were made to close the communication gap at the practice level. The IntensivKontakt study is an interprofessional project to investigate the effects of digital patient-practitioner-relative communication (trilateral) on the mental and physical recovery and health of patients in intensive care units and their relatives.

Population

Adult patients hospitalised in intensive care units and their family members, who have experienced virtual communication during the patients hospital stay
- excluded are: palliative setting, neonatal-pediatric intensive care units, nursing home settings, inpatient elderly not in intensive care units

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

All forms of telecommunication: text messages, voice messages, phone calls, video calls

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Adult patients hospitalised in intensive care units and their family members, who have not experienced virtual communication during the patients hospital stay

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

- Patient: depression, anxiety, stress, loneliness, satisfaction, vital signs, quality of life, PTSD (PICS)
- Relatives: depression, anxiety, stress, loneliness, satisfaction, quality of life, PTSD (PICS)

Additional outcomes

Experience data from medical practitioners

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction (selection and coding)

The initial electronic database search resulted in 13389 citations. After removing the duplicates, 11148 citations were left for the screening process. All titles and abstracts were screened by two reviewers independently. The first screening resulted in 150 studies to obtain the full-text version. Assessing these according to the inclusion criteria, 120 papers were excluded; 50 did not examine the appropriate intervention, 20 did not have the specified patient population and four full-text papers were not obtainable. Additionally, two further citations are included to follow a consultation with an expert. In total, forty-three citations were included. Patient and family outcome data will be extracted, both quantitative and qualitative, also by two independent reviewers, using the following format from Cochrane: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). Data collection form. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2017. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-specific-resources-review-authors

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

For the assessment, RoB-tools from Cochrane will be applied

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

For the mixed-method systematic review (MMSR), the Convergent segregated approach will be applied.

- Step 1: Independent synthesis of quantitative (descriptive analysis including meta-analysis of RCT data, followed by narrative synthesis of these) and qualitative studies (meta-aggregation)
- Sept 2: The findings of each single method synthesis included in this review will then be configured according to the JBI methodology for MMSR. This will involve quantitative evidence and qualitative evidence juxtaposed together and organized/linked into a line of argument to produce an overall configured analysis

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

None

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

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Funding source

Sponsored by a nonprofit foundation (Klaus Groth). There is no affiliation between this review and the foundation.

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TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Review timeline

Start date: 01 April 2024. End date: 01 June 2025

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

25 January 2025

Date of registration in PROSPERO

05 February 2025

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Publication of review results

The intention is to publish the review once completed. The review will be published in English

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work		
Formal searching/study identification		
Screening search results against inclusion criteria		
Data extraction or receipt of IP		
Risk of bias/quality assessment		
Data synthesis		

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Additional information

There has been few systematic reviews reporting the effect of telecommunication between patients and families on ICUs. This new review paper will accentuate the concept of 'family involvement' as a 'digital form' on ICUs and its impact on patient and family outcomes, expanding the scope of the theme.

PROSPERO version history

- Version 1.1 published on 05 Feb 2025
- Version 1.0 published on 05 Feb 2025

Review conflict of interest

None known

Country

Germany

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